

Photorefractive Integrated Photonics for Analog Signal Processing in AI

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Abstract—The computational cost of AI could be alleviated by accelerating the synaptic transfer calculations in artificial neural networks with an analog crossbar array processor. In this work, we present the core building blocks of an all-optical integrated photorefractive crossbar array for artificial neural network training by demonstrating photorefractive synapses in an integrated 2-D beam interaction network. We show that the photorefractive quality of the circuits resembles that of the bulk GaAs crystal that they were fabricated from. Then, this work experimentally validates the integrated photorefractive crossbar array design and constitutes a framework for engineering photorefractive integrated photonics.

Index Terms—Analog crossbar multiply-accumulate (MAC) accelerator, holographic photonic memory, in-memory computing, integrated photonics, photorefractive effect, synapses.

I. INTRODUCTION

MACHINE Learning is fueling an unsustainable compute demand [1]. In particular, the synaptic signal transfer between Artificial Neural Network (ANN) layers is computationally expensive. Namely, the corresponding matrix-vector multiplication (MVM) of the synaptic weights and the input neural signals generates a multiply-accumulate (MAC) workload that scales quadratically with ANN width.

This synaptic signal transfer operation is a promising target for analog signal processing by a crossbar array (Fig. 1(a)) [2]. Firstly, ANNs typically require a low computational accuracy [3]. Crucially, the MVM is performed with a mere linear power scaling on ANN width: each output neuron simply requires a constant analog signal power budget. The benefit of analog MVM processing for ANNs is implied by system level analysis [4].

Numerous hardware implementations of analog crossbar array processors have been conceived, both in electronics and photonics, each with merits and trade-offs [5], [6], [7], [8].

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Fig. 1. (a) Analog crossbar array processor concept. The analog input neural signal amplitudes s are transmitted to output signal lines by an array of tunable coupling elements into which the synaptic weight matrix W is programmed, yielding the synaptic signal transfer operation Ws . (b) A photonic crossbar array hardware concept. The photorefractive effect is used to write a hologram that diffracts laser beams in accordance with the synaptic weight matrix. (c) The photorefractive crossbar array in integrated photonics.

Fig. 2. Photonic integrated circuits (PIC) made from semi-insulating GaAs for the demonstration of individual photorefractive synapses. (a) A picture of the chip (lower right), the waveguide cross-section (upper right), and a transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of the top GaAs-SiO₂ interface (left), showing crystalline GaAs and the material transition layer. (b) The 2-D beam interaction network circuit (Fig. 1(c)) consisting of a horizontal (H) and vertical (V) vector branch. Two beams interfere to form a photorefractive synapse. The index contrast between GaAs and SiO₂ is sufficient to enable sidewall mirrors by total internal reflection.

In this work, we target an all-optical photonic design that exploits the photorefractive effect (Fig. 1(b)) [2], [9], [10]. In a photorefractive crystal, the fringe pattern by two interfering laser beams drives the formation of a holographic Bragg grating with a tunable diffraction strength based on the applied optical write energy. The grating constitutes a tunable synaptic coupling element between laser beams representing neural signals. Due to their angular selectivity, Bragg gratings may be spatially superimposed to program the entire 2-D synaptic interconnect network in a single hologram.

The photorefractive crossbar architecture has special desirable properties. If a write-vector is enabled in both the horizontal and vertical processor branch (Fig. 2(b)), rather than a single

write-beam pair, the weight matrix is updated according to their outer product, thereby enabling efficient ANN backpropagation training [2], [10]. Additionally, the photorefractive synaptic weights update effectively continuously, thereby assisting training convergence. The utilization of photorefractive synapses does not cause lasting damage or wear for a perfect crossbar lifetime. Scaling is assisted by an intrinsic robustness against local manufacturing variations by the merit of spatially superimposed and spread out synapses, and holography offers a high photonic storage density [11]. Lastly, the photorefractive effect can be leveraged to optically emulate a non-linear neural activation response, although not within the scope of this paper [12].

Photorefractive crossbar array processors have been demonstrated with free-space bulk-optical setups [9], [10]. Our research goal is to transfer the concept to a photonic integrated circuit (PIC) for enhanced scalability, robustness, and economics (Fig. 1(c)) [2]. Additionally, the laser coherence length can be relaxed, as dictated by the maximum optical path length difference. To this end, it needs to be shown that PICs can be realized of adequate photorefractive quality compared to bulk crystal. Specifically, circuit fabrication may impair the photorefractive crystal properties and material boundary effects may become of significance. For instance, photorefractive charge trapping has been reported in the SiO₂ cladding of waveguides with an LiNbO₃ core [13].

In our previous work, we describe the fabrication of photorefractive PICs by etching and polishing down a bonded semi-insulating GaAs wafer to yield a $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ thick GaAs-on-insulator layer, into which beam interaction network circuits were patterned (Fig. 2) [2], [14]. We selected GaAs for wavelength compatibility with silicon photonics, for potential heterogeneous integration, relatively easy circuit processing, and photonic platform maturity [2], [15].

In this work, we lay the foundations for an integrated photorefractive crossbar array processor by validating its design principles. Specifically, we demonstrate photorefractive synapses in a prototype 2-D beam interaction network by two-wave mixing (Fig. 2(b)), and benchmark the photorefractive quality of the PIC against bulk GaAs crystal of the same ingot.

II. DESIGN GOAL

For context, we elaborate on the estimated potential of the photorefractive crossbar array design, based on the general projections for photonics [16]. Our design goal is a 1000×1000 matrix in a $\sim 1\text{cm}^2$ 2-D beam interaction network (Fig. 2(b)) [11]. Larger fully connected ANN layers can be spread-out across multiple chips [4]. A large array alleviates the conversion cost per MAC operation of the I/O vector data between the digital electrical and analog optical domains [16], [17]. Our estimates indicate instead an efficiency bottleneck by the crossbar optical power consumption, yielding an estimated ~ 100 TOPs/W for neural network inference, assuming a fully diffraction efficiency optimized GaAs crystal. This represents 1 to 2 orders of magnitude improvement compared to current digital hardware [18]. The targeted minimum vector coefficient compute resolution is 4-bits, which can be enhanced by increasing the optical

Fig. 3. The physical mechanisms underlying photorefractive two-wave mixing. (a) Two monochromatic laser beams arbitrarily labeled as ‘source’ S and ‘destination’ D intersect, (b) and yield a sinusoidal intensity interference pattern. (c) By localized photoexcitation, the optical fringe pattern drives the redistribution of electrons, trapped inside crystal impurities, (d) yielding a phase-shifted space-charge electrical field. (e) By the linear electro-optic effect, the electric field generates a volume Bragg grating, (f) onto which beams D and S diffract. (g) The associated beam energy exchange may in turn affect the fringe pattern.

Fig. 4. 2-D beam interaction model for photorefractive two-wave mixing between beams S and D . (a) The beams are modeled by a square envelope, ignoring diffraction, and thus yield a diamond-shaped intensity fringe pattern. (b) Similarly, the phase-grating is assumed diamond-shaped with an amplitude given by the unbounded plane-grating solution. (c) The diffraction of D on the grating yields a scattering coefficient s_D , which by symmetry can be obtained from plane wave diffraction on an effective slab Bragg grating.

power budget [3]. Finally, integrated photonics should enable adequately low channel crosstalk [19].

III. METHODS

A. Photorefractive Two-Wave Mixing Theory for GaAs

We develop a model for photorefractive two-wave mixing so that the photorefractive quality of the GaAs PIC may be compared to the bulk crystal underlying its fabrication. The physical model mechanisms are outlined in Fig. 3 [20]. The high-level performance parameters of interest are the maximum hologram diffraction efficiency (amplitude) and the photorefractive responsiveness (write speed). The remaining high-level performance metric is the dark retention time, which we ignore as it is only of significance when the average optical input intensity is low, for instance, for storage applications.

In our experiments, the hologram size is typically limited by the beam width rather than the sample size, while the beam amplitudes are approximately constant in the propagation direction. Therefore, we do not adopt the popular results from 1-D coupled-mode theory [12]. Instead, we develop a 2-D diffraction model for the explicit incorporation of the hologram size (Fig. 4), based on a doubly undepleted beam approximation so that step **g** in Fig. 3 can be ignored for a constant Bragg grating amplitude.

We derive the expressions for our experimental alignment (Fig. 5) and step-by-step for Fig. 3(b) to (f). The potential impact of wave guiding will be considered. We restrict the study to beam D , because the expressions for the source beam S follow

Fig. 5. Crystal-beam alignment for maximum photorefractive coupling between two s-polarized beams in GaAs [12].

by symmetry considerations. We treat the steady-state response first, after which we discuss time-dependence.

1) *Intensity Fringe Pattern:* In the (x', y') reference frame (Fig. 4(a)) and ignoring the square beam envelope, S and D are described by plane waves

$$\mathbf{A}_D = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_D D e^{i(\omega t - \mathbf{k}_D \cdot \mathbf{r})} \quad (1)$$

with intensity-normalized complex amplitude

$$D = \sqrt{I_D} e^{-i\phi_D}. \quad (2)$$

For s-polarization, $|\mathbf{k}_D| = |\mathbf{k}_S| = n_{\text{eff}} k_0$, with $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda$ the optical wave vector amplitude in vacuum and n_{eff} the mode refractive index. In the absence of waveguiding, n_{eff} reduces to the baseline material refractive index n_0 .

The optical fringe pattern follows from the total field $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_D + \mathbf{A}_S$ as

$$I = \mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{A} = I_0 (1 + m \cos(Kx' + \Delta\phi_{DS})) \quad (3)$$

with $K = 2k_0 n_{\text{eff}} \sin(\theta)$ the grating wave vector amplitude, θ the half beam intersection angle (Fig. 4(a)), $I_0 = I_D + I_S$ the combined beam intensity, $\Delta\phi_{DS} = \phi_D - \phi_S = 0$ the beam phase-mismatch that vanishes by aligning the reference frame with a fringe peak, and

$$m = 2|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_D \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}_S| \sqrt{I_D I_S} / I_0 \quad (4)$$

the fringe pattern visibility, where we retain the polarization inner product for completeness.

2) *Space-Charge Redistribution:* The Kukhtarev-Vinetskii (KV) model provides the most widely adopted description of the photorefractive charge dynamics [21]. We consider the case of free electrons as the single charge carrier, no photovoltaic effect or external electrical field, and a low optical intensity I_0 that is high enough for the photoconductivity to dwarf the dark conductivity. This yields for the fundamental Fourier component of the steady-state space charge distribution [22]

$$\rho_1 = m\mathcal{P} \cos(Kx' + \Delta\varphi) \quad (5)$$

with the reduced grating amplitude given by

$$\mathcal{P} = \frac{k_B T \varepsilon}{e} \frac{K^2}{1 + K^2/k_D^2}. \quad (6)$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, e the elementary charge, and ε the static dielectric constant. In writing ε , we assume an isotropic material. The *reduced* amplitude \mathcal{P} means that it is the grating amplitude compensated for the optical intensity, thereby it constitutes the maximum

addressable charge density since $m \leq 1$ (4). For completeness, we include a phase mismatch $\Delta\varphi$ between the intensity fringe pattern and the charge grating, which vanishes in our study by symmetry considerations. k_D is the inverse Debye screening length

$$k_D = e \sqrt{\frac{N_e}{k_B T \varepsilon}} \quad (7)$$

and determines at what value of K the grating formation becomes limited by inhibited carrier transportation due to the emerging space-charge electric field. Lastly, the effective charge trap density is given by

$$N_e = \frac{[N_+][N_0]}{[N_+] + [N_0]} \quad (8)$$

with $[N_+]$ and $[N_0]$ the emptied and filled deep trap densities in the dark respectively.

Based on (6), we can discriminate between a diffusion-limited regime ($K \ll k_D$)

$$\mathcal{P}_d = \frac{k_B T \varepsilon}{e} K^2 \quad (9)$$

and a charge-limited regime ($K \gg k_D$)

$$\mathcal{P}_q = e N_e. \quad (10)$$

Equation (5) is generally considered valid for $m \ll 1$, since it is derived by linearizing the KV model [22], [23], [24]. Under the aforementioned conditions, N. V. Kukhtarev showed that the extension for m close to unity requires the modification $m \rightarrow 2(\sqrt{1+m^2}-1)/m$ in the diffusion-limited regime ($K \ll k_D$) [21]. Since this modification is marginal ($< 20\%$), we ignore it. The validity of (5) for large m has been suggested before [20].

3) *Space-Charge Field:* The spatial charge distribution ρ_1 yields an electrical space-charge field by Gauss's law

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}' m E_{\text{sc}} \sin(Kx' + \Delta\varphi) \quad (11)$$

with reduced amplitude

$$E_{\text{sc}} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon K} \mathcal{P}. \quad (12)$$

4) *Refractive Index Modulation:* \mathbf{E}_{sc} yields a Bragg grating by the linear electro-optic effect

$$n = n_0 + \Delta n \sin(Kx' + \Delta\varphi). \quad (13)$$

The effective amplitude can be conveniently obtained by the tensor product [25]

$$\Delta n_{ab} = -\frac{1}{2\varepsilon_0^2 \sqrt{n_a n_b}} \hat{\mathbf{b}} \cdot \bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{(0)} [\bar{\bar{r}} \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}}] \bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{(0)} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}} \quad (14)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$ the input and output beam polarization respectively, n_a and n_b their refractive indices, ε_0 the vacuum permittivity, $\bar{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{(0)}$ the unperturbed dielectric tensor, and $\bar{\bar{r}}$ the Pockels tensor.

Our experimental configuration (Fig. 5) yields a grating amplitude [12]

$$\Delta n = -m \frac{1}{2} n_0^3 r_{41} E_{\text{sc}} \quad (15)$$

with r_{41} the Pockels coefficient of GaAs. The sign of r_{41} flips depending on the crystal orientation with respect to \hat{x}' (Fig. 4(a)).

In the case of a photorefractive waveguide core, (13) needs to be modified for the mode index

$$n = n_{\text{eff}} + \Gamma \Delta n \sin(Kx' + \Delta\varphi). \quad (16)$$

Δn is weighed by the mode confinement factor Γ to approximate the sensed grating amplitude [26]. More generally, Γ is given by the projection of the scattered pump beam core field on the output mode profile, which is not the confinement factor for cross-polarization coupling due to the electric field profile mismatch between TM and TE modes.

5) *Diffraction on a Bragg Grating*: We derive the complex scattering coefficient s_D associated with the diffraction of beam D on the holographic Bragg grating, which in our model corresponds to plane wave diffraction on a slab slanted phase-grating (Fig. 4(c)). This problem was famously solved by H. Kogelnik, however, the coupled-wave theory deployed there is incompatible with different *effective* gratings for S and D (Fig. 4) [27]. Instead, we deploy a linear model for weak diffraction, and s_D is retrieved as the combined action of thin grating segments dz that are illuminated by an undepleted beam D while consecutive higher-order diffraction components are ignored. Since this approach is relatively light-weight while capturing the relevant physics for the photorefractive crossbar array, we discuss it in detail.

We start with deriving the signal from a single grating segment dz , where we take inspiration from the work done on diffraction on acoustic waves [28]. In the rotated reference frame, \hat{z} is aligned with the grating surface normal (Fig. 4(c)). Equation (14) takes care of polarization besides potential index and mode changes, and the vectorial component of the electric field will be omitted. Per grating-slice dz , a sinusoidal phase modulation is imprinted into the wavefront of D

$$E_D(z + dz) = E_D(z) \cdot t(x, z) \quad (17)$$

with transmission function, assuming $dz / \cos(\phi) \ll K^{-1}$,

$$t(x, z) = e^{-ik_0 n(x, z) dz / \cos(\phi)}. \quad (18)$$

Here, ϕ is the angle between the wave vector \mathbf{k}_D and the grating surface normal \hat{z} (Fig. 6(a)).

The refractive index is given by (16)

$$n(x, z) = n_{\text{eff}} + \Gamma \Delta n \sin(K[x \sin(\varphi) + z \cos(\varphi)] + \Delta\varphi) \quad (19)$$

with φ the angle between the grating wave vector \mathbf{K} and the grating surface normal \hat{z} (Fig. 6(a)).

The transmission function t can be expanded in terms of Bessel functions [28]

$$t(x, z) = e^{-i \frac{k_0 n_{\text{eff}} dz}{\cos(\phi)}} \cdot \sum_{p=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(J_p \left[\frac{\Gamma k_0 \Delta n dz}{\cos(\phi)} \right] \cdot e^{-ip[K \sin(\varphi)x + K \cos(\varphi)z + \Delta\varphi]} \right) \quad (20)$$

Fig. 6. (a) K-vector diagram for photorefractive two-wave mixing with parallel polarization coupling (Fig. 4(c)). Beam D with wave vector \mathbf{k}_D generates two diffraction components \mathbf{k}_p (blue) per grating segment dz and with phase mismatch per grating width $\Delta k_{z,p}$. (b) The grating width required for the $p = 1$ order to pick up 2π in phase mismatch $l_{2\pi}$, expressed in number of optical periods λ/n_{eff} . For $2\theta > 90^\circ$, no $p = 1$ order exists. Since $l_{2\pi}$ is of order λ , $p = 1$ can usually be ignored.

and setting $dz \rightarrow 0$

$$t(x, z) \approx e^{-i \frac{k_0 n_{\text{eff}} dz}{\cos(\phi)}} \cdot \left[1 + \sum_{p=-1,1} \left(p \cdot \frac{\Gamma k_0 \Delta n dz}{2 \cos(\phi)} \cdot e^{-ip[K \sin(\varphi)x + K \cos(\varphi)z + \Delta\varphi]} \right) \right]. \quad (21)$$

From this expression, we immediately see that, if the transmission function t is applied to beam D (1), upon decomposing $E_D(z + dz)$ at the z -plane, two first order diffraction orders $p = -1$ and $p = 1$ appear with wave vectors modified in accordance with

$$k_{x,p} = n_{\text{eff}} k_0 \sin(\phi) + pK \sin(\varphi) \quad (22)$$

and relative amplitudes

$$a_p = p \frac{\Gamma k_0 \Delta n}{2 \cos(\phi)} e^{-ip[K \cos(\varphi)z + \Delta\varphi]} dz. \quad (23)$$

The complex scattering coefficient s_p is obtained by collecting the diffraction components from all grating segments. We do this at the hologram center where D and S are in-phase so that the phase of s_p is conveniently given with respect to both. Aligning the reference frame origin with the hologram center and ignoring the depletion of D

$$s_p = \int_{-\frac{w_S}{2}}^{\frac{w_S}{2}} \frac{a_p}{dz} e^{-ik_0 n_{\text{eff}} \cos(\phi) z} e^{ik_0 n_{\text{eff}} \cos(\phi_p) z} dz = p \frac{\Gamma k_0 \Delta n}{2 \cos(\phi)} e^{-ip\Delta\varphi} \int_{-\frac{w_S}{2}}^{\frac{w_S}{2}} e^{-i\Delta k_{z,p} z} dz \quad (24)$$

with

$$\Delta k_{z,p} = k_0 n_{\text{eff}} \cos(\phi) + pK \cos(\varphi) - k_0 n_{\text{eff}} \cos(\phi_p) \quad (25)$$

the phase-mismatch factor consisting respectively of the phase of the pump, the phase induced by the grating, and the phase collected by mapping to the hologram center.

Equations (22) and (25) can be intuitively understood based on the appropriate k-diagram (Fig. 6(a)). We notice that only $p = -1$ is phase-matched corresponding to the direction of beam S , and generally only for parallel polarization coupling for which the scattered and pump beam refractive indices are the same.

Using $\Delta k_{z,-1} = 0$ and $\phi = \pi/2 - 2\theta$, the scattering coefficient from beam D to beam S is obtained from (24) as

$$s_D \equiv s_{-1} = -\Gamma \frac{\pi \Delta n w_S}{\lambda \sin(2\theta)} e^{i\Delta\varphi}. \quad (26)$$

The expression for S follows from (24) by using $p = 1$ and w_D instead (Fig. 6(a))

$$s_S = \Gamma \frac{\pi \Delta n w_D}{\lambda \sin(2\theta)} e^{-i\Delta\varphi}. \quad (27)$$

Lastly, we consider the potential experimental clipping of the hologram by introducing the actual versus maximum grating surface area ratio C . The scattering coefficient attenuates linearly if diffraction effects are ignored, and the real scattering coefficient becomes

$$r_D = C s_D. \quad (28)$$

In case the hologram area is limited solely by the sample width d and assuming equal beam widths $w_S = w_D = w$

$$C = \begin{cases} \frac{d \sin(\theta)}{w} \left(2 - \frac{d \sin(\theta)}{w} \right), & \text{for } \left| \frac{d \sin(\theta)}{w} \right| < 1, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

As $d|\sin(\theta)|/w$ approaches 0 for narrow samples, C effectively modifies the interaction length from $w/\sin(2\theta)$ to $d/\cos(\theta)$, upon which $|r_D|$ with $\Gamma = 1$ matches the result of 1-D two-wave mixing models for doubly undepleted beam coupling [12], [29].

6) *Power Exchange*: We derive the power exchange between optical beams S and D due to their diffraction on the photorefractive grating. We limit ourselves to identical beam widths w so that no normalization is needed and $|r_S| = |r_D| \equiv r$. Both beams are s-polarized (Fig. 5) and interfere directly for an output amplitude $D' = D + r_S S$ and intensity

$$I'_D = D'^* D' = I_D - 2r \sqrt{I_D I_S} \cos(\Delta\varphi) + \mathcal{O}(r^2) \quad (30)$$

with I'_D and I_D the intensity with and without grating respectively. We note that transmission loss may be ignored to linear approximation.

After filling in the appropriate definitions as derived previously and setting $\Delta\varphi = 0$, the normalized steady-state photorefractive power exchange $\Delta P_D = P'_D - P_D$ is obtained as

$$\frac{\Delta P_D}{P_D} = -\frac{I_S}{I_D + I_S} \frac{\Gamma C r_{41} n_0^3 w}{4n_{\text{eff}} \epsilon \sin^2(\theta) \cos(\theta)} \mathcal{P} \quad (31)$$

where we note that $\Delta P_D/P_D = \Delta I_D/I_D$.

7) *Time-Dependence*: In general, the grating formation follows an overdamped oscillatory behavior [22], [23]. In our experiments, the simplified exponential saturation expression is adequate, yielding a synaptic scattering coefficient (weight) (26)

$$w(t) = -m s_{\text{max}} e^{i\Delta\varphi} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}) + w_0 e^{-t/\tau} \quad (32)$$

with w_0 the boundary condition for $t = 0$, and $s_{\text{max}} = |s_D|/m$ (26) the maximum scattering coefficient amplitude.

If the grating is being written with a relative phase offset, upon noting that $\Delta\phi_{DS}$ (3) enters in the same manner as $\Delta\varphi$ (5), this can be included in (32) by redefining the fringe visibility (4) as

$$m = |m| e^{i\Delta\phi_{DS}} = 2D^* S/I_0. \quad (33)$$

For writing holographic matrices W , instead of a single write beam pair S and D , multiple inputs are activated in the processor simultaneously. This yields write beam vectors \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{D} , with their coefficients given by the complex optical input amplitudes in the respective processor branch (Fig. 2(b)). The interaction between forming gratings can be ignored besides an increase in background radiation I_0 [10]. Then, assuming a constant maximum diffraction strength s_{max} and response time τ by negligible variations in the grating wave vector \mathbf{K} , the matrix W formation is obtained by replacing m by the visibility matrix $M = D^* \otimes S / (|D|^2 + |S|^2)$ (32). This yields all the matrix operations required for ANN backpropagation training [2]:

- 1) forward propagation $\mathbf{S}_{\text{out}} = W\mathbf{D}$;
- 2) backward propagation $\mathbf{D}_{\text{out}} = -W^\dagger \mathbf{S}$;
- 3) synaptic weight update $\Delta W \propto \mathbf{D} \otimes \mathbf{S}$.

Because the optical power modification scales linearly with the grating amplitude (31), (32) yields experimentally for two-wave mixing

$$P'_D(t) = \Delta P_D (1 - e^{-t/\tau}) + \Delta P_0 e^{-t/\tau} + P_D. \quad (34)$$

B. Photorefractive Responsiveness

For low optical intensities, the grating formation speed is limited by the rate at which charge is photoexcited, and the response time scales inversely with the optical intensity [12]

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \mathcal{R} \cdot I_0 \quad (35)$$

with \mathcal{R} the photorefractive responsiveness.

Expressions for \mathcal{R} can be retrieved from the KV-model. Using the same assumptions that yielded the steady-state grating amplitude ρ_1 (5) [22]

$$\mathcal{R} = \Gamma_{\text{die}}^* \frac{1 + K^2/k_D^2}{1 + K^2/k_c^2} \quad (36)$$

with k_D once again the inverse Debye screening length (7),

$$k_c = \sqrt{\frac{e}{k_B T \mu \tau_R}} \quad (37)$$

the inverse carrier diffusion length, and

$$\Gamma_{\text{die}}^* = e\alpha\Phi\mu\tau_R/\epsilon h\nu \quad (38)$$

the inverse dielectric relaxing rate τ_{die}^{-1} corrected for the optical intensity I_0 . Here, μ is the carrier mobility, τ_R the carrier recombination time, α the absorption constant, and Φ the quantum efficiency.

There are three variables in (36): the effective trap density N_c , a diffusion metric $\mu\tau_R$, and the photorefractive absorption constant $\alpha\Phi$. In our experimental setup, holes are the main charge

TABLE I
PHOTOREFRACTIVE QUALITY PARAMETERS

Metric	Measured	Performance	Material
Amplitude	$\Delta P_D/P_D$ (34)	\mathcal{P} (31)	N_e (6)
Write time	τ (34)	\mathcal{R} (35)	$\alpha\Phi/N_e$ (36) & (39)

carrier, in which case the latter two expressions reduce further to $\tau_R = 1/\gamma_h[N_0]$ and $\alpha = s_h[N_+]$, with γ_h the hole recombination coefficient and s_h the hole excitation cross section [22].

We shall see that the regime of experimental interest is for small gratings periods $K \gg k_c$ and $K \gg k_D$. Then, the diffusion length does not play a role, and the excitation governed responsiveness is obtained from (36) as

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{ex}} = \frac{\alpha\Phi}{N_e} \frac{1}{h\nu} = \frac{s_h\Phi}{h\nu} \frac{[N_+]}{N_e}. \quad (39)$$

In $\alpha\Phi/h\nu \cdot I_0$ we recognize the carrier density generation rate which is normalized by the movable charge density N_e to yield the inverse exponential response time $1/\tau$ (35).

1) *Summary:* We summarize in Table I the photorefractive two-wave mixing theory for assessing the photorefractive GaAs quality based on the experimental configuration outlined in Fig. 5. In terms of the hologram strength, the measured steady-state relative power modification $\Delta P_D/P_D$ (34) yields the reduced grating amplitude \mathcal{P} by (31), from which the material effective deep trap density N_e is resolved by (6). For the write speed, the measured exponential response time τ is compensated for the optical intensity to yield the photorefractive responsiveness \mathcal{R} (35), which connects to the relative photorefractive absorption $\alpha\Phi/N_e$ for small grating periods (39).

C. Experimental Setup

Our goal is to experimentally measure photorefractive synapse formation by two-wave mixing (34), so that the effective trap density N_e and the relative photorefractive absorption constant $\alpha\Phi/N_e$ can be resolved and compared between PIC and bulk GaAs crystal (Table I).

The experimental setups are outlined in Fig. 7. Grating write sequences are triggered by applying $0 \leftrightarrow \pi$ phase-shifts to the source beam by an electro-optical phase modulator (EOPM) and a square wave drive signal with a transient response much faster than the photorefractive response time τ . Then, if the grating is allowed to saturate, based on (34) with $\Delta P_0 = -\Delta P_D$, the optical response becomes

$$P'_D(t) = \Delta P_D \left(1 - 2e^{-t/\tau}\right) + P_D. \quad (40)$$

Thus, phase-modulation is attractive since hologram erasure is automatically taken care of, and the power modulation can be doubled compared to the saturated grating ΔP_D .

Since \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{R} generally depend on the grating wave-vector K , ideally the bulk crystal is measured at the same half beam intersection angle $\theta = 45^\circ$ as the PIC (Fig. 7). For the free-space setup (Fig. 7(a)), refraction limits the maximum intersection angle to about $\theta = 17^\circ$ inside the crystal. Depending on the experiment, we circumvented this limit by rotating the sample 45° in R_y to have beam S enter the sample via the [100] facet.

Fig. 7. Schematic overview of the experimental setups for photorefractive two-wave mixing with semi-insulating GaAs. (a) A free-space bulk-optical setup for measuring bulk crystal samples. (b) A fiber-optical setup for measuring PICs, with the red text denoting optical transmission losses. The experimental designs are mostly identical besides notably the beam power splitting ratio of 1:1 (free-space) and 1:4 (PIC). Specifically, in setup (b), the 1:9 output by the fiber splitter yields 1:4 after the optical bench transmission losses.

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS (FIG. 7)

	PIC	Bulk 0°	Bulk 45°
θ_0 [deg]	-	30, 45, 60	30, 45, 60
θ [deg]	45	8.5, 12, 14.8	40.6, 45, 49.4
w [mm]	0.2	1.6^\dagger	1.6^\dagger
w_y [mm]	6e-4	1.6	1.6
d [mm]	-	3 ; 10	10
Γ	0.99	1	1
n_{eff}	3.34	3.4	3.4
r_{eff}	r_{41}	r_{41}	$r_{41}/\sqrt{2}$
T [dB]	-25	0^*	0^*
δ	4	1	1
C	1	$0.5^\dagger ; 1$	1

θ_0, θ : half beam intersection angle outside and inside the sample (Fig. 7(a)), w : in-plane beam width, w_y : out-of-plane beam width, d : sample width, Γ : confinement factor, n_{eff} : mode index, r_{eff} : effective Pockels coefficient, T : transmission loss from laser to beam interaction area, δ : beam splitting ratio I_S/I_D , C : hologram clipping factor. Values with a \dagger and $*$ are respectively refraction and reflection corrected depending on θ_0 during analysis in order to account for the air-to-GaAs interface.

Table II lists experimental parameters. Notably, we set the beam widths equal to the $\pm 1/e$ Gaussian beam field points.

The laser wavelength was set to 1356.38nm for an optimal transmission through the 2-D interconnect circuit (Fig. 7(b)) [2]. The photorefractive synaptic response is generally not sensitive to sub nm wavelength shifts, as governed by the grating wave vector amplitude K and the photoexcitation cross section s (39) [22], [30]. However, exciting both electrons and holes should generally be avoided to prevent a hologram amplitude reduction, with 1356.38nm indicating holes as the dominant charge carrier [24], [30], [31].

Lastly, based on Table II, the optical background intensity by the model square beams (Fig. 4) is obtained from the laser power

Fig. 8. Photorefractive two-wave mixing time traces with the exponential fit model from (34). Graphs (a) and (b) show experiments for the PIC for 12 mW and 3 mW laser power respectively. Graph (c) shows two-wave mixing in bulk GaAs crystal and at the same beam intersection angle θ (Fig. 7(a)).

as

$$I_0 = P_{\text{laser}} \cdot T / (w \cdot w_y). \quad (41)$$

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 8 shows the two-wave mixing experimental data. The optical power modulates in time due to the periodic rewriting of the photorefractive synapse each time the S beam is π phase-shifted by the EOPM. Graphs (a) and (b) demonstrate that the response time τ increases by decreasing the optical intensity (35). In the legend, the fitted response times are given with \pm the standard error as estimated by fitting the four write events separately.

Fig. 9 shows the exponential fit results of the two-wave mixing traces (Fig. 8) for the relative steady-state power modification $\Delta P_D/P_D$ and inverse response time τ^{-1} (34). The y error bars denote the fit robustness 95% confidence interval (Fig. 8). The fit values are presented with \pm the standard error.

From $\Delta P_D/P_D$ and τ , we obtain the reduced amplitude \mathcal{P} and responsiveness \mathcal{R} by (31) and (35) respectively. The combined results are presented in Fig. 10. This includes bulk crystal data at numerous half beam intersection angles θ (Table II). Only the data for the thick bulk GaAs sample (*Bulk 10 mm* and *Bulk 45°*) is fitted to constitute the benchmark. In the fit for \mathcal{R} (36), the effective trap density N_e was not used as a free parameter in favor of using the value obtained by fitting \mathcal{P} . Likewise, the diffusion constant $\mu\tau_R$ could not be fitted reliably by the absence of data at low K , so that we applied a ballpark figure of $1e-11 \text{ m}^2/\text{V}$ [22]. The error bar corresponds to the 95% confidence interval based

Fig. 9. Photorefractive relative steady-state power exchange (a) and inverse response time (b) (34) as extracted from the optical traces (Fig. 8) versus optical intensity I_0 for two-wave mixing inside the PIC. The intensity scaling relations are presented in (31) and (35) respectively.

Fig. 10. Fundamental photorefractive performance metrics (a) reduced grating amplitude \mathcal{P} (5) and (b) responsiveness \mathcal{R} (35) as function of grating wave vector amplitude K . The fit models are shown in (6) and (36) respectively. N_e is the effective photorefractive trap density that dictates \mathcal{P} , and thereby the maximum hologram diffraction efficiency, for large K (10). $\alpha\Phi$ is the photorefractive absorption cross section that governs the rate at which the grating charge is optically generated and dictates \mathcal{R} , and thereby hologram write speed, for large K (39).

on a standard error comprised of the experimental fit uncertainty and a 10% and 25% standard error in I_D and I_S for bulk and PIC respectively. The intensity error margin for the PIC we estimate larger due to the instability of fiber array coupling (Fig. 7) and potentially varying waveguide facet quality.

V. DISCUSSION

In this work, a primary goal is to show synaptic connections in the 2-D slab waveguide interconnection network to prove the viability of the integrated photorefractive crossbar array design. Indeed, the measurements in Fig. 8(a)–(b) clearly demonstrate the successful writing of photorefractive synapses. Moreover, Fig. 9 demonstrates the desired formation behavior that enables neural network back propagation training: a constant steady-state grating amplitude and an inversely decreasing response time based on the background radiation I_0 [2].

Next, we aim to identify any potential change in the photorefractive quality of the PIC compared to the bulk GaAs crystal. Starting with the visual differences in the two-wave mixing traces (Fig. 8), the ripple present on the optical signal for the PIC can be attributed to an unstable Fabry-Pérot interference, likely by laser wavelength fluctuations. Specifically, the integrated circuit with cleaved sidewalls constitutes an optical cavity (Fig. 7(b)). Such instabilities are increasingly visible at a reduced relative beam power exchange.

The photorefractive quality results are shown in Fig. 10, where firstly we note that the obtained model fit parameters are within expectations. The effective EL2 trap density of around $2.5e14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is comparable to a density of around $1e15\text{--}cm^{-3}$ reported by another group [31]. The photorefractive absorption constant $\alpha\Phi = 1.8\text{--}m^{-1}$ is compatible with compound semiconductors, albeit strongly dependent on trap type, trap density, and wavelength. Specifically, for InP:Fe $\alpha\Phi = 2.7\text{--}m^{-1}$ has been observed [22].

The significance of the results in Fig. 10 is ultimately determined by the validity of the model. Notably, for the responsiveness \mathcal{R} , the 3 mm wide sample shows variations compared to the 10 mm sample even though they are made from the same material. We attribute these variations to differences in optical background intensity, arising from Fabry-Pérot resonances in the 3 mm sample. Multiple overlapping beam round trips are possible with an intersection angle $\theta \approx 10^\circ$, $w > 1.6 \text{ mm}$, and $d = 3 \text{ mm}$, whereas the model assumes the singular intersection of two beams (Fig. 4). Next, the reduced grating amplitudes \mathcal{P} retrieved at low K are less than predicted by the charge model (Fig. 10(a)), which can be partially explained by the omission of the appropriate model modification for m close to unity.

We consider the decrease in the reduced grating amplitude \mathcal{P} for the PIC (Fig. 10) significant, and conclude that the effective trap density N_e has approximately halved compared to bulk (10). Simultaneously, the ratio $[N_+]/N_e$ appears preserved for an unaltered responsiveness \mathcal{R} (39).

The effective trap density N_e can either lower by a reduction in trap density, or a shift in the dark trap occupation ratio (8). In the studied crystal, the native EL2 trap is responsible for the photorefractive effect, yielding a non-zero N_e due to the promotion of $[N_+]$ by a carbon shallow acceptor impurity [22]. It is unlikely that circuit fabrication lowered the EL2 trap density. Specifically, EL2 annealing requires temperatures of $\sim 800^\circ\text{C}$, whereas our fabrication thermal budget is 400°C [2], [32]. Likewise, the thermal modification of carbon has not been reported even at 900°C [33]. Then, these results suggest that N_e

is limited by $[N_+]$ for a constant $[N_+]/N_e$ (8), and that $[N_+]$ has decreased in the PIC by the introduction of a donor impurity, potentially at the GaAs - SiO₂ interface (Fig. 2(a)).

The effective trap density N_e is important for a performant crossbar array processor with a high hologram diffraction efficiency. Specifically, considering a half beam intersection angle $\theta = 45^\circ$ (Fig. 2(b)), we introduce the maximum photorefractive diffraction per unit interaction-length $\gamma = s_{\text{max}}/w = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} n_0^3 r_{\text{eff}} E_{\text{sc}}/2m$ (26) & (32) as a figure of merit, taking the form

$$\gamma_q = \frac{\sqrt{2}e}{8} \left[\frac{N_e n_0^2 r_{\text{eff}}}{\varepsilon} \right] \quad (42)$$

in the charge-limited hologram regime (10), until it reaches the diffusion-limited (9) maximum value

$$\gamma_d = \frac{2\pi^2}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{k_B T}{e} \left[\frac{n_0^4 r_{\text{eff}}}{\lambda^2} \right]. \quad (43)$$

The obtained effective trap density for the PIC $N_e \sim 1.5e14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Fig. 10(a)) yields a charge-limited performance $\gamma_q \sim 0.6 \text{ m}^{-1}$. Increasing N_e to $1e17 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ would yield $\gamma \sim 35 \text{ m}^{-1}$, close to the diffusion-limited maximum $\gamma_d \sim 39 \text{ m}^{-1}$, implying over 3 orders of magnitude improvement in diffraction efficiency $\eta \propto \gamma^2$.

The integrated crossbar array processor design is not restricted to GaAs, and for a discussion on photorefractive materials we refer to M. Cronin-Golomb and M. B. Klein [20]. Based on γ_d (43), it is implied that ferroelectric oxides enable maximum diffraction efficiencies by large Pockels coefficients r_{eff} and compatibility with optical wavelengths $\lambda \sim 500 \text{ nm}$. Notably, X-cut lithium niobate (LiNbO₃) represents a relatively mature photonic platform, boasting $r_{\text{eff}} \approx r_{13} \sim 9 \text{ pm/V}$ and $\gamma_d \sim 315 \text{ m}^{-1}$ (14) [29], [34], [35]. This represents an approximate tenfold uplift in γ_d compared to GaAs, enabling crossbar compute efficiencies approaching ~ 1000 TOPs/W by lifting the predicted optical power consumption bottleneck [17]. Moreover, factoring in the photovoltaic effect, γ for LiNbO₃ should surpass γ_d [20]. X-cut barium titanate (BaTiO₃) could be an alternative, with a similar r_{13} , but requiring the electrical poling of its crystallographic domains [36].

Besides diffraction efficiency, the material importantly affects the responsiveness \mathcal{R} (36) and the diffraction-limited processor size. The diffraction-limited hologram area scales with the wavelength $A \propto \lambda^2/n_0^2$, and does not compete with γ_d (43) [11]. The responsiveness \mathcal{R} should generally be low to avoid significant hologram bleaching within a number of computations proportional to the matrix size. We intend to achieve this by using a laser wavelength with an adequately low photoexcitation cross section s (39) regardless of the material [22].

Lowering the photorefractive photoexcitation cross section additionally lowers the associated absorption loss. At 1356.38 nm , the EL2 absorption cross section is $s_h \sim 0.6e-16 \text{ cm}^2$, implying an transmission loss of -0.04 dB by using $[N_+] = N_e \sim 1.5e14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and a circuit length of $\sim 1 \text{ cm}$ (Fig. 7(b)) [30]. This would increase to -26 dB for the proposed $N_e = 1e17 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, implying the necessity of lowering s_h by two orders of magnitude by a modified wavelength.

Of the -10 dB insertion loss reported for the circuit in Fig. 7(b), we can attribute -6 dB to a distorted network transmission by GaAs substrate thickness inhomogeneities, and -4 dB by waveguide propagation loss [2]. With increased manufacturing maturity, the circuit insertion loss should become limited by the 2-D network transmission (Fig. 2(b)). Specifically, the sidewall mirrors induce wavefront aberrations that can only be partially accounted for by optimizing the input and output waveguide layout and shape [37]. This limit remains to be demonstrated.

Lastly, we have ignored the dark hologram lifetime. However, for applications where the average photoconductivity is low, based on the discussed KV-model, the impact of the dark conductivity can be modeled by an effective background intensity term $I_0 = I_D + I_S + I_{\text{Dark}}$ in (4), (32), and (35), as governed by the $1/e$ dark lifetime and responsiveness $\tau_{\text{Dark}}^{-1} = \mathcal{R}I_{\text{Dark}}$ (35). For GaAs, the dark lifetime $\tau_{\text{Dark}} \sim 10$ s at $K \sim 20 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ is relatively short [38]. LiNbO₃ would enable dark lifetimes of months instead, and supports semi-permanent hologram fixing techniques [20], [39].

VI. CONCLUSION

We demonstrate photorefractive synapses in an integrated photonic 2-D interaction network, proving the viability of the crossbar design. Indeed, a full crossbar would be achieved by adding two multi-channel input stages to the existing hardware design for setting different input vectors (Fig. 2(b)). Additionally, the hologram diffraction efficiency needs to be enhanced by an optimized photorefractive material. This material could be GaAs with an increased effective photorefractive charge trap density, but a ferroelectric oxide material, such as LiNbO₃, could enable even higher performance.

The GaAs integrated circuits display a photorefractive quality closely matching the bulk crystal that they were manufactured from. Importantly, the effective trap densities are of the same order of magnitude. Based on this result, we conclude that thinning down bulk crystal is a viable manufacturing strategy for integrated photorefractive photonics. Simultaneously, our results highlight that the photorefractive quality of photonic integrated circuits cannot be taken for granted.

In a broader context, this work outlines an experimental and theoretical framework for engineering photorefractivity into integrated photonics. We predict that the photorefractive effect will constitute a valuable building block beyond the application of MAC acceleration. For example, to achieve integrated high-density memory or coherent beam amplification.

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